

Studies on the Dependence of Optical Rotatory Power on Chemical Constitution. Part XIII.
Naphthylene Derivatives of Stereoisomeric Iminocamphors and Methylenecamphors.

BY BAWA KARTAR SINGH AND BHUTNATH BHADURI.

In the present communication we give an account of our experiments on the optical rotatory dispersion of the condensation products of camphorquinones (*d*, *l*, *dl*) and oxymethylenecamphors (*d*, *l*, *dl*) with naphthylenediamines (1:2 and 1:5).

1:2-Benzocamphanoquinoxalines (*d*, *l*) prepared by us melts at 116-17° and the *racemic* form at 123-24° (*vide* Experimental). Heckendorn (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1929, 12, 50) records 85-86° as the melting point of the *dextro* compound. Our repeated attempts to isolate a compound having this low melting point have failed and in the absence of any experimental data we provisionally assume it to be a dimorphous form of the compound prepared by us; but as no data of rotatory power are given by Heckendorn, for the lower melting compound, it is not possible for us to give a definite opinion on this point.

The condensation products of oxymethylenecamphors (*d*, *l*, *dl*) with 1:2-naphthylenediamine are oils which refused to solidify. The condensation products of camphorquinones (*d*, *l*, *dl*) with 1:5 naphthylenediamine consist of two different types of compounds, *viz.*, 1:5-naphthylenebisiminocamphor (VII) and 1-amino-5-naphthyliminocamphor (X) which can be separated by fractional crystallisation (*vide* Experimental).

Compounds described in the paper have been examined with a view to find the effect of (1) chemical constitution and (2) nature of solvent on the rotatory power and the results are as follows.

(1) The effect of a ring structure on rotatory power is very well brought out by comparing the structural formulae of phenyliminocamphor (I) and α -naphthyliminocamphor (III) with those of camphanoquinoxaline (II) prepared by Singh and Majumdar (*J. Chem.*

Soc., 1919, **115**, 566) and 1:2-benzocamphanoquinoxalines (IV) respectively.

$$[\alpha]_D = +726.6^\circ \text{ (chloroform).}$$

(Forster and Thornley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 944).

$$[\alpha]_D = +28.5^\circ \text{ (chloroform).}$$

$$[\alpha]_D = +609.6^\circ \text{ (chloroform).}$$

$$[\alpha]_D = -29^\circ \text{ (chloroform).}$$

(Singh and Mazumdar, *loc. cit.*).

The doubly linked oxygen atom of the carbonyl group in the aryl derivatives of iminocamphor is replaced by a doubly linked nitrogen atom of the azethenoid group with the ring closure in the *ortho* position in the quinoxaline derivatives. This change in structure (I→II; III→IV) has produced phenomenal depression in the rotatory power of camphanoquinoxaline and in the case of 1:2-benzocamphanoquinoxalines even the sign of the rotatory power has changed. Other cases of depression of rotatory power on ring formation have already been noticed by one of us (Singh and Biswas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 1895; Singh and Puri, *ibid.*, 1926, p. 504) for the aryl derivatives of camphoramides and camphorimide; *e.g.*, the following are the values of $[M]_D$ in ethyl alcohol; camphorbenzylamic acid (99.88°)→camphorbenzylimide (30.19°); camphor-*m*-nitrobenzylamic acid (106.7°)→camphor-*m*-nitrobenzylimide (31.92°); camphor- β -naphthylamic acid (229°)→camphor- β -naphthylimide (60°). Again the rotatory powers of esters of 1-methyl-3-cyclopentanone-4-carboxylic acid are about 30 times as great as those of the corresponding esters of methyladipic (Haller, *Compt. rend.*, 1905, **140**, 1205) and the hexahydrophthalic acids have much lower rotatory power than their anhydrides (Werner, *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 3046). This is even more strikingly illustrated in the case of monosaccharides.

The rotatory power of *d*-mannitol is $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -0.2^\circ$ (Fischer, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3684) whereas that of *d*-mannonolactone is $+53.8^\circ$ (Fischer, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 3219). The high rotatory power of most of the sugars as compared with the corresponding polyhydric alcohol is a proof of the ring structure of the former. The increase which is brought about in the rotatory power of sugar alcohols by boric acid is attributed to the formation of ring complexes.

It is thus possible to infer from these and other examples that the rotatory power of a cyclic compound is usually very considerably different from that of the corresponding open chain derivative. It may be greater or less. It is also seen from these examples that the increase or decrease in the rotatory power resulting from ring formation cannot be correlated with the fact that the asymmetric centre lies *within* or *without* this ring.

The rotatory power of 1:5-naphthylenebisiminocamphor (VII) is considerably less than one half the value of the rotatory power of the 1:4 compound (V). It is nearly one half the value of *p*-phenylenebisiminocamphor (VI). The low value of the rotatory power of 1:5-naphthylenebisiminocamphor is due to the fact that the conjugation between the carbonyl, azethenoid groups and the naphthalene ring is broken at the *fifth* carbon atom in the naphthalene nucleus (Table A, VII) whereas these conjugation is complete in the case of 1:4-naphthylenebisiminocamphor, and *p*-phenylenebisiminocamphor. The rotatory power of 1:5-naphthylenebisaminomethylene camphor (IX) is only slightly lower than the corresponding 1:4-compound (VIII). The break in the conjugation at the fifth carbon atom in the naphthalene nucleus being distant from the asymmetric centre has very little effect, the greater effect being produced by another break in the conjugation at the secondary amino group which is near the asymmetric centre, and is present in both the compounds.

The introduction of an amino-group in the 5-position of α -naphthyliminocamphor (X) lowers the rotation of the parent compound and the acetylation of the amino-group further lowers the same (XI).

2. The rotatory power of the compounds is higher in pyridine and benzene and lowest in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol, which is approximately in the inverse order of the dielectric constants of the solvents.

TABLE A.

Structural formula.	$[\alpha]_D$ in chloroform	References
V. C_8H_{14} (9 conjugated double bonds)	1941°	Sinha & Bhaduri, <i>J. Indian Chem. Soc.</i> , 1930, 7, 548.
VI. C_8H_{14} (7 conjugated double bonds).	1527°	Singh & Bhaduri, <i>ibid.</i> , p. 548.
VII. C_8H_{14} (Conjugation broken between the carbon atoms marked 4 & 5 and is shown by the dotted line when counted round the shortest route).	787°	
VIII. C_8H_{14} (conjugated broken at the dotted line) _e	569°	Singh & Bhaduri, <i>ibid.</i> , p. 789.
IX. C_8H_{14} (conjugation broken at the dotted lines and arrow).	435°	

Except for 1:5-naphthylenebisaminomethylenecamphor the rotatory dispersion for the remaining compounds was studied only for about 3 wave-lengths as the substances were so highly coloured that the lines beyond Hg_{5780} towards the violet end of the visible region of the spectrum could not be viewed through the solution. 1:5-Naphthylenebisaminomethylenecamphor, like the other derivatives of oxymethylenecamphors, obeys the simple dispersion equation of Drude, $[\alpha]$

$$= \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}. \text{ The values of rotatory power of } d \text{ and } l \text{ forms in different}$$

solvents (Tables I-V) are identical within limits of experimental error. Out of 66 observations now recorded, in as many as 47 cases, the difference in the numerical value of specific rotatory power of the opposite isomers corresponds to a difference of less than $0\cdot01^\circ$ in the observed angle of rotation and in 17 other cases the corresponding angle lies between $0\cdot01^\circ$ to $0\cdot02^\circ$ which is the limit of experimental error allowable in such measurements. Only in the remaining 2 cases, *viz.* 1:2-benzocamphanoxinoxaline in pyridine for Hg_{violet} and for 1-acetylamino-5-naphthyliminocamphor in pyridine for Na_D (Table

IV), the difference corresponds to between $0\cdot02^\circ$ and $0\cdot03^\circ$ in the observed angle of rotation. These however, are of the nature of casual experimental errors. This therefore, further supports Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry, according to which the two forms, *dextro* and *laevo*, must possess equal and opposite rotatory power.

Whether a *racemic* form is a *dl*-compound of the *d* and *l* isomers can be sometimes inferred from the melting point determinations.

Three cases may arise: (a) The melting point of the *racemic* form is higher than that of the active forms, in which case it is a true *dl*-compound, at least in the solid state. The *racemic* form of benzocamphanoquinoxaline is an instance of this nature. (b) The melting point of the *racemic* form is lower than that of the opposite active forms, as in the case of 1-amino-5-naphthyliminocamphor. (c) The melting point of the *racemic* form is identical with that of the active forms, as in the case of 1:5-naphthylenebisaminomethylenecamphor. In (b) and (c) other experiments will have to be made before it can be settled whether the *racemic* form is a *dl*-compound or a mixture of the *d* and *l* forms. Examples of *racemic* forms having identical melting points with the active forms are very rare. In our studies we have, up till now, come across only two other instances, namely, camphorquinones (*d*, *l*, *dl*) which melt at 198°-99° and *oo'*-stilbenebisaminomethylenecamphors (*d*, *l*, *dl*), m.p. 295-96° (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 190). Other examples which may be cited are:— π monobromocamphor, m.p. 92·4° (Kipping and Pope, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, **97**, 372); limonene- α -nitrosochloride, m.p., 103·04° (Wallach, *Annalen*, 859, **111**, 125,252); phenylhydrazide of gulonic acid, m.p. 147-49°, and of galactonic acid, m.p. 200·05° (Fischer, *Ber.*, 1894, **27**, 3225); phenylgulosazone, m.p. 157·59° (Fischer, *Ber.*, 1892, **25**, 1030).

EXPERIMENTAL.

1:2-Benzo-*d*-camphanoquinoxaline.—*d*-Camphorquinone (1 mol.) in ethyl alcoholic solution was added to the aqueous solution of 1:2-naphthylenediamine hydrochloride (1 mol.) and heated in presence of fused sodium acetate at 60° for 45 minutes. The condensed product was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution shaken with concentrated hydrochloric acid sufficient to dissolve the reddish yellow precipitate first formed. The reddish acid layer was separated and diluted with water when a voluminous yellow mass was precipitated. The alcoholic solution was just neutralised with ammonia and crystallised as white prisms melting at 116-17°, yield, 35 p.c. (Found: C, 83·37; H, 6·80; N, 10·00. $C_{20}H_{20}N_2$ requires C, 83·33; H, 6·94 and N, 9·73 per cent.). It is freely soluble in the ordinary organic solvents. Benzo-*l*-camphanoquinoxaline, m.p. 116-17°. (Found: N, 9·73. $C_{20}H_{20}N_2$ requires N, 9·73 per cent.). Benzo-*dl*-camphanoquinoxaline, m.p. 123-24°. (Found: N, 10·02. $C_{20}H_{20}N_2$ requires N, 9·73 per cent.).

Benzo-d-camphanoquinoline could not be reduced even when heated with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid.

1:5-Naphthylenebisiminocamphor and 1-Amino-3-naphthylimino-camphor.—*d*-Camphorquinone (1.7 g.) was heated with 1:5-naphthylenediamine hydrochloride (2.3 g.) in presence of fused sodium acetate at 99-100° for 8 hours. The condensed product extracted with alcohol contained both the compounds which were separated by fractional crystallisation out of ethyl alcohol in which the bisimino compound is sparingly soluble. First crop, brown amorphous solid, infusible even at 260°, yield, 0.3 g. Second crop: (from the filtrate) after repeated crystallisation from dilute alcohol, yellowish orange crystals (probably prisms) melting at 192-93° were obtained (yield, 1.1 g.).

1:5 Naphthylenebisimino-d-camphor, infusible even at 260°, fairly easily soluble in chloroform, pyridine, benzene and acetone; sparingly soluble in alcohols (ethyl and methyl) and ether. (Found: N, 6.40. $C_{30}H_{34}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6.17 per cent.).

1-Amino-5-naphthylimino-d-camphor, yellowish orange prisms, m.p. 192-93°, freely soluble in ordinary organic solvents including ether. (Found: C, 78.22; H, 7.37; N, 9.03 and 9.29. $C_{20}H_{22}ON_2$ requires C, 78.43; H, 7.19 and N, 9.15 per cent.).

1:5-Naphthylenebisimino-l-camphor, infusible even at 260°. (Found: N, 6.25. $C_{30}H_{34}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6.17 per cent.). *1:5-Naphthylenebisimino-dl-camphor*, infusible even at 315°. (Found: N, 6.24. $C_{30}H_{34}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6.17 per cent.).

1-Amino-5-naphthylimino-l-camphor, m.p. 192-93°. (Found: N, 9.40. $C_{20}H_{22}N_2O$ requires N, 9.15 per cent.). *1-Amino-5-naphthylimino-dl-camphor*, m.p. 172-73°. (Found: N, 9.36. $C_{20}H_{22}ON_2$ requires N, 9.15 per cent.).

1-Acetylamino-5-naphthylimino-d-camphor.—*1-Amino-5-naphthylimino-d-camphor* was acetylated in the usual way with acetic anhydride and the acetyl compound crystallised out of dilute alcohol as greenish yellow prismatic crystals melting at 173-74°. (Found: C, 75.71; H, 7.13; N, 8.31. $C_{22}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires C, 75.85; H, 6.90; N, 8.05 per cent.). It is freely soluble in the ordinary organic solvents.

1-Acetylamino-5-naphthylimino-l-camphor, m.p. 173°-74°. (Found: C, 75.71; H, 7.14; N, 8.09. $C_{22}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires C, 75.85; H, 6.90; N, 8.05 per cent.).

1:5-Naphthylenebisaminomethylene-*d*-camphor.—Oxymethylene-*d*-camphor (1.8 g.) in methyl alcohol and 1:5-naphthylenediamine-hydrochloride (1.15 g.) in glacial acetic acid with a little fused sodium acetate, were mixed together when a greenish yellow precipitate separated at once. It was crystallised out of pyridine as shining yellow crystals (probably prisms) melting at 322-23°. (Found: C, 79.56; H, 8.08. $C_{32}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires C, 79.65; H, 7.88 per cent.). It is fairly soluble in chloroform; less so in pyridine and sparingly soluble in benzene, acetone, ether, ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol.

1:5-Naphthylenebisaminomethylene-*l*-camphor, m.p. 322-23°. (Found: N, 5.87. $C_{32}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.81 per cent.). Rotatory power was determined only in chloroform, the substance being sparingly soluble in other solvents. 1:5-Naphthylenebisaminomethylene-*dl*-camphor, m.p. 322-23°. (Found: N, 5.92. $C_{32}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.81 per cent.).

TABLE I.

1:2-Benzocamphanoquinoxaline.						
Solvent	Conc. g/100 c.c.	<i>d, l,</i> or <i>mean.</i>	Hg _{violet} [α]	Hg _{gree} [α]	Hg _{yellow} [α]	Na _D [α]
Pyridine	1.0020	<i>d</i>	-127.2°	-51.29°	-42.41°	-39.92°
	1.0056	<i>l</i>	+125.8	+50.71	+42.26	+39.27
Benzene	1.0040	<i>d</i>	-117.9	-46.30	-38.33	-26.33
	1.0012	<i>l</i>	+116.9	+46.45	+37.96	+35.96
Chloroform	1.0008	<i>d</i>	-91.37	-36.97	-30.48	-28.98
	1.0032	<i>l</i>	+92.22	+37.39	+30.40	+29.42
Acetone	1.0040	<i>d</i>	-35.36	-13.94	-11.45	-10.46
	1.0008	<i>l</i>	+34.47	+13.49	+10.99	+9.99
Ethyl alcohol	1.0008	<i>d</i>	-33.93	-13.50	-10.99	-10.00
	1.0036	<i>l</i>	+33.40	+12.96	+10.96	+9.47
Methyl alcohol	1.0060	<i>d</i>	—	-0.99	-0.49	-0.49

TABLE II.

1:5-Naphthylenebisiminocamphor.

Solvent.	Conc. g/100 c.c.	<i>d, l,</i> or <i>mean.</i>	Hg _{yellow} [α]	Na _D . [α]
Benzene	0.0516	<i>d</i>	+1037.0°	+959.3°
	0.0500	<i>l</i>	-1040.0	-960.0
Pyridine	0.0500	<i>d</i>	+940.0	+880.0
	0.0512	<i>l</i>	-937.6	-878.8
Acetone	0.0516	<i>d</i>	+930.3	+872.0
	0.0504	<i>l</i>	-922.6	-863.0
Chloroform	0.0540	<i>d</i>	+78.70	+740.9
	0.0516	<i>l</i>	-794.5	-736.4

Hg_{green} line was very indistinct when viewed through these solutions. Rotations in alcohols (ethyl and methyl) could not be obtained as the substance was very difficultly soluble in them.

TABLE III.

1-Amino-5-naphthyliminocamphor.

Solvent	Conc. g/100 c.c.	<i>d, l,</i> or <i>mean.</i>	Hg _{yellow} [α]	Na _D [α]
Pyridine	0.1000	<i>d</i>	+725.0°	+675.0°
	0.1016	<i>l</i>	-723.5	-669.2
Benzene	0.1008	<i>d</i>	+689.5	+644.8
	0.1020	<i>l</i>	-686.3	-642.2
Acetone	0.1016	<i>d</i>	+649.7	+600.5
	0.0996	<i>l</i>	-652.5	-602.4
Chloroform	0.1000	<i>d</i>	+600.0	+565.0
	0.1008	<i>l</i>	-595.3	-560.6
Ethyl alcohol	0.1004	<i>d</i>	+597.5	+562.7
	0.1000	<i>l</i>	-600.0	-560.0
Methyl alcohol	0.1004	<i>d</i>	+577.7	+542.8
	0.1000	<i>l</i>	-575.0	-540.0

Hg_{green} line was very indistinct when viewed through most of these solutions; through others it was not at all visible.

TABLE IV.

1-Acetylamino-5-naphthyliminocamphor.

Solvent.	Conc.	<i>d, l,</i>	Hg _{green}	Hg _{yellow}	Na _D
	g/100 c.c.	or <i>mean.</i>	[α]	[α]	[α]
Pyridine	0.2008	<i>d</i>	+814.4°	+635.0°	+602.7°
	0.2000	<i>l</i>	-810.0	-630.0	-597.5
Benzene	0.2000	<i>d</i>	+802.5	+622.5	+587.5
	0.2012	<i>l</i>	-802.8	-623.8	-586.5
Acetone	0.2012	<i>d</i>	+653.8	+519.4	+492.0
	0.2000	<i>l</i>	-652.5	-517.5	-487.5
Chloroform	0.2000	<i>d</i>	+637.5	+507.5	+480.0
	0.2020	<i>l</i>	-636.0	-507.7	-482.6
Ethyl alcohol	0.2008	<i>d</i>	+597.7	+478.2	+450.8
	0.2024	<i>l</i>	-600.2	-479.2	-454.4
Methyl alcohol	0.2000	<i>d</i>	+557.5	+440.0	+416.8
	0.2020	<i>l</i>	-559.4	-443.1	-420.7

TABLE V.

1:5-Naphthylenebisaminomethylenecamphor in chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{79.47}{\lambda^2 - 0.1646} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.4057.$$

Dextro				Laevo			
concentration	obs. [α]	o—cLine.	calc. [α]	o—c	obs. [α]	concentration	
g/100 c.c.	o		c		o	g/100 c.c.	
0.3984	+843.4°	-1.1°	Cd ₅₀₈₆ ±844.5°	+0.4°	-344.9°	0.4048	
	745.4	+0.5	Ag ₅₂₀₉ 744.9	-0.2	744.7		
	594.8	±0	Hg ₅₄₆₁ 594.8	+0.6	595.4		
	468.1	-0.7	Hg ₅₇₈₀ 468.8	+0.1	468.9		
	435.4	+0.4	Na ₅₈₉₃ 435.0	-0.3	434.7		
	382.3	+0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄ 382.0	+0.9	382.9		
	317.5	-0.5	Cd ₆₄₃₈ 318.0	-0.6	317.4		
	278.6	+0.2	Li ₆₇₀₈ 278.4	-0.5	277.9		

The solution did not exhibit any mutarotation.

The rotatory power determinations were made in a 2 dcm. jacketed tube at 35°. Hg_{violet}, Hg_{green}, Hg_{yell.} and Na_D refer to the violet mercury line 4358, the green mercury line 5461, the yellow mercury line 5780, and the yellow sodium line 5893 respectively. In the case of 1:5-naphthylenebisaminomethylenecamphor (Table V), which shows simple rotatory dispersion, the value of λ_0 has been calculated from the dispersion formula, and is expressed as μ or 10^{-4} cm.

We wish to make grateful acknowledgment to the Government of Bihar and Orissa in the ministry of Education, for the grant of a research scholarship to one of us (B.B.) which has enabled him to take part in this investigation.